

MOTIVATION OF PEDAGOGICAL BACHELORATE GRADUATES FOR PROFESSIONAL TEACHING ACTIVITIES

Sh.Sh. Khaidarov

Teacher of the field of Pedagogy Shahrissabz State Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10439489>

Abstract. *The article presents the results of a study conducted by the author on the motivation of graduates of a pedagogical bachelor's degree for professional teaching activities. The author analyzed the theoretical aspects of educational and professional motivation, selected methods that allow assessing the current level of professional and pedagogical motivation and motives for professional activity.*

Keywords: *professional development, professional pedagogical activity, motivation for professional activity, professional motivation, motives for professional activity.*

Motivation for professional teaching activities on the part of students is a multi-level process. Since the very concept of motivation is multifaceted, therefore the approaches to defining and identifying developmental features are extensive.

There are different approaches to defining the essence of motivation. E.P. Ilyin considers motivation as the essence and mutual process of external and internal forces or motivations for any activity [1].

Analyzing domestic research devoted to educational motivation, it can be noted: many authors agree that the basis of motivation is human needs, which are created only on the basis of the essence of a person [2], [4], [5].

G.D. Nemtsova notes that when entering a new educational institution, students' motivation is determined mainly by their new social role [3]. But it cannot support his educational work for a long time and gradually loses its importance. Therefore, the formation of motives that give meaningful meaning to learning is one of the main tasks of the teacher. Educators and psychologists highlight the role of positive motivation for learning in ensuring the successful acquisition of knowledge and skills.

Analyzing the learning process of students, it is necessary to note the uniqueness of the formation of educational and professional motivation. According to E.A. Garaeva, students' motivation is manifested based on the time they devoted to the university [7].

As noted by O.P. Sterligov and K.G. Apresyan, in the formation and manifestation of educational and professional motivation of former schoolchildren who enter vocational education institutions, motives such as interest, gaining freedom and, of course, acquiring a new status through entering a new environment appear, first of all. The interest, most often, is not due to the specific professional field that they expect to enter in the future, but because they like the very fact of a "new stage of life", they are leaving the point to which they have been tied for many years. Gaining freedom: students feel that they will now become more free in relation to previous years of study, they will be able to become independent and make decisions. Acquiring a new status is associated with entering a qualitatively new environment, communication with teachers and other students, a system of new relationships and updated content and forms of educational and cognitive activity [6].

Students who study in the 2nd-3rd year form completely different motives for educational professional activities. Professional competencies are being formed, students study their profession more, immerse themselves in the practical process, and use the acquired knowledge in practice. The final segment of students are graduates. 4th year students master scientific research methods, form professional attitudes, the need for self-realization and self-actualization, learn the principles of professional ethics, develop a creative research approach, and skills in analyzing the results of their work.

Motivation for future professional activity should manifest itself already during the period of training in professional educational programs. A student's educational and professional motivation consists of the following elements:

1. Focusing on the learning situation.
2. Awareness of the meaning of the upcoming activity.
3. Conscious choice of motive.
4. Goal setting.
5. Striving for a goal (carrying out educational activities).
6. The desire to achieve success (awareness of confidence in the correctness of one's actions).
7. Self-assessment of the process and results of activity (emotional attitude to activity).

These components determine the possible directions of formative and corrective influence when organizing work to develop motivation in students for their upcoming professional activities.

To determine the current level of professional pedagogical motivation and motives for professional activity, we conducted a survey. The study involved final year undergraduate students in the areas of training Pedagogical Education and Pedagogical Education (with two profiles of training) in the amount of 80 people.

To assess the general level of motivation for students' professional activities, we used the test "Self-assessment of professional and pedagogical motivation" (author N.P. Fetiskin) [8, p. 79-80]. The methodology allows us to determine at what level of the "motivational ladder" the respondent is, whether he is characterized by indifference, episodic superficial curiosity, interest, developing curiosity, functional interest is developing, or the pinnacle is being reached - the professional need to consciously study pedagogy and master the basics of pedagogical skills.

The results obtained will allow us to form a certain picture of students' motivation for professional teaching activities. The results obtained are presented in Figure 1.

Rice. 1. Summary results of the distribution of students in pedagogical fields by level of professional pedagogical motivation (according to N.P. Fetiskin's method ; n = 80 people; November 2022)

The results obtained are determined by such characteristics as: professional need (PP), functional interest (FI), developing curiosity (RL), ostentatious interest (OS), episodic curiosity (EL), indifferent attitude (RO). All these characteristics formed the levels that are shown in the figure.

Thus, students (20% of the total sample) have a high level who are inquisitive, active, have a need to gain professional knowledge, are interested in demonstrating their knowledge and engaging in scientific activities in order to gain knowledge and experience.

Average level (30% of the total sample): these are students who are occasionally involved in the process of professional activity. They understand that they are getting a profession, which is why they must understand certain material. At the same time, they show insufficient professional activity.

Low level (50% of the total sample): such students are inactive, they are not interested in educational and professional activities, or in applying the acquired knowledge in practice. Most often they attend classes "for show" and do poor quality work.

The data obtained demonstrate certain results of general professional motivation, however, it is necessary to determine in what directions the professional pedagogical motivation of students exists and develops.

To identify the motives for educational and professional activities, we used the methodology "Diagnostics of the motives for the professional activities of specialists" (author T.N. Frantseva) [9].

The results of the study are presented in Figure 2.

Rice. 2. Summary results of the study of the motives for the educational and professional activities of students in pedagogical fields (according to the methodology of T.N. Frantseva ; n = 80 people; November 2023)

The results obtained indicate that mostly graduate students, when thinking about motivation, prioritize recognition (65%), learning the material that will help them gain recognition (62%), and for more than half of the participants, self-realization is important (55%). The least attractive motives are life support (41%) and interaction (33%).

Thus, we can conclude that graduates of the pedagogical bachelor's degree are not sufficiently motivated for professional teaching activities. The results of their mastery of a professional educational program in the form of knowledge, abilities, skills, competencies can hardly be successfully applied in real professional activities after students receive a diploma of higher pedagogical education. It is necessary to organize and carry out targeted work throughout the entire training to develop motivation for professional activity.

REFERENCES

1. Ilyin E.P. Motivation and motives. St. Petersburg: Peter, 2011. 512 p.
2. Kharlamova T.M. Professional self-determination of graduates of a pedagogical university. Advances of modern natural science. 2008. No. 2. P. 64-66.
3. Nemtsova G.D. The relationship between the motivation of educational and professional activities and the socio-psychological adaptability of first-year students // Current problems of psychology and pedagogy in modern education: Materials of the international scientific and practical conference. Yaroslavl, March 31, 2017 Yaroslavl: YarSPU im. K.D. Ushinsky, 2017. 310 p. pp. 308-310.
4. Tkach R.S., Tkach E.N. Motivation to achieve success as a subjective resource in the educational and professional activities of university students. Problems of higher education. 2019. No. 1. P. 446-449.
5. Slastenin V.A. Formation of a teacher's personality in the process of professional training [Text] / V.A. Slastenin . – M.: Education, 1996. – 160 p.
6. Sterligova O.P., Apresyan K.G. Specifics of motivation for students' educational and professional activities when entering and graduating from a university. Development of professionalism. 2019. No. 1. P. 53-55.
7. Garayeva E.A. Study of university students' motivation for educational and professional activities. Azimuth scientific research: pedagogy and psychology. 2019. Vol. 8. No. 1 (26). pp. 62-65.
8. Fetiskin N.P., Kozlov V.V., Manuilov G.M. Socio-psychological diagnostics of personality development and small groups. M.: Publishing house of the Institute of Psychotherapy. 2002. 362 p.
9. Frantseva T.N. Questionnaire for diagnosing the motives of professional activity of specialists. Bulletin of the Samara Humanitarian Academy. Series: Psychology. 2010. No. 2 (8). pp. 146-160.
10. © Khaidarov Sh.Sh., 2023.